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Abbreviations

AFW	Auxiliary Feed Water
BRU-A	Steam dump valve to-atmosphere
BWR	Boiling Water Reactor
CVCS	Chemical and Volume Control System
DBA	Design Basis Accident
DEC	Design Extension Conditions
DG	Diesel Generator
ECCS	Emergency Core Cooling System
EFW	Emergency Feedwater
EOP	Emergency Operating Procedures
EPR	European Pressurised Reactor
FA	Fuel Assemblies
FP	Fission products
HFP	Hot Full Power
HPIS	High Pressure Injection System
IE	Initiating Event
LB	Large Break
LOCA	Loss of Coolant Accident
LOOP	Loss Of Offsite Power
LPCI	Low Pressure Coolant Injection
LPIS	Low Pressure Injection System
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MCP	Main Cooling Pump
MFW	Main Feed Water
MSIV	Main Steam Isolation Valve
MSLB	Main Steam Line Break
PCT	Peak Cladding Temperature
PORV	Power Operated Relief Valve
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
PRZ	Pressurizer
RCS	Reactor Cooling System
RHRS	Residual Heat Removal System
RPV	Reactor Pressure vessel
RV	Relief Valve
RWST	Refuelling Water Storage Tank
SCRAM	Safety Control Rod Axe Man
SDA	Steam Dump to Atmosphere
SEG	Senior Expert Group
SG	Steam Generator
SG SRV	Steam Generator Safety Relief Valves
SG SV	Steam Generator Safety Valve
SGTR	Steam Generator Tube Rupture
SI	Safety Injection
SLB	Steam Line Break
SLBOUT	Steam Line Break Out of containment
VVER	Water Water Energy Reactor
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The R2CA project (Reduction of Radiological Consequences of design basis and extension Accidents) targets the development of harmonized methodologies and innovative management approach and safety devices for the evaluation and for the reduction of the consequences of DBA and DEC-A accidents in operating and foreseen nuclear power plants in Europe. For both purposes, the development of methodologies will be conducted with the goal of better estimate the safety margins using less conservative approaches (more realistic assumptions). This will reinforce the confidence on these safety margins for conditions up to the extended design domain, will allow the identification of new accident management measures and devices and will support the optimization of the potential associated emergency population protection measures. Improvement of evaluations tools will be supported by the reassessment of the existing experimental and analytical databases.

In this document are presented the results, analyses and conclusions from first simulation runs of selected Loss Of Coolants Accidents (LOCA) and Steam Generator Tube Ruptures (SGTR) in different kind of LWRs (PWRs, BWR, VVERs and EPR) within DBA and DEC-A conditions. These transients, being by nature completely different and involving different physical phenomena, have been selected at the very beginning of the project by a dedicated Senior Expert Group (SEG) as representative bounding scenarios to quantify the gains obtained by code and methodology improvements. Analyses of the first simulation run results are intended to help and confirm the orientation for the improvements of the codes for the two representative categories of accidents, LOCA and SGTR. This deliverable will serve as a reference point for task 2.5 where a second run of simulations of the same LOCA and SGTR transients will be performed with improved models and calculation chains.

The gain obtained from the improvement of evaluations tools and methodologies will be demonstrated by comparing the first and second calculation runs. Analysis of the second simulation run results will have to confirm the gain obtained from the improved models and upgraded calculation schemes and help in the proposal of harmonized methodologies for the evaluation of the radiological consequences of these transients.

For both categories, the simulation scheme supporting best estimate evaluations can be outlined starting from the target of the radiological consequences by a systematic identification of the involved phenomena and associated issues.

2 First run of reactor test case simulations

The first run of simulations of the reactor cases selected by the SEG has been performed using existing simulation tools of various details at different scales in various calculation schemes. These calculations have provided a large range of results that were post-processed and analysed.

In total, 13 organizations participated in this task, with LEI as leading organization. These organizations have provided LOCA and/or SGTR simulations for DBA and/or DEC-A conditions. The list of organizations involved, their analysed type of reactor, the chosen scenario and accidental conditions are presented in Table 1.

Organization	Type of reactor	LOCA		SGTR	
		DBA	DEC-A	DBA	DEC-A
ARB	VVER-440	+	+	+	+
	VVER-1000	+	+	+	+
Bel V	PWR-1000	-	-	+	+
BOKU	PWR-1300	-	-	+	+
	VVER-1000	-	-	+	+
CIEMAT	PWR-1000	-	-	+	+
ENEA	PWR-900	+	+	-	-
HZDR	PWR-Konvoi	+	+	-	-
IRSN	PWR-900	+	+	+	-
LEI	BWR-4	-	+	-	-
EK	VVER-440	+Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.	-	+	-
SSTC-NRS	VVER-1000	+	+	+	+
TRACTEBEL	PWR-1000	-	-	+	+
UJV-NRI	VVER-1000	+	-	+	-
VTT	EPR-1600	+	-	-	-
	VVER-1000	-	+	-	-

Table 1. Partners in T2.3, analysed type of reactors, accident scenarios and conditions.

2.1 Summary of analysed reactor types

As mentioned already in Table 1 in the framework of task 2.3 different reactor types have been analysed.

- VVER type reactors have been analysed by 6 partners:
 - VVER-1000 was analysed by ARB, BOKU, SSTC-NRS, UJV-NRI and VTT. This is a 3000 MW_{th} and 1000 MW_e reactor with four primary loops, four MCPs and four horizontal SGs.
 - VVER-440 was analysed by ARB and EK. Both partners analysed the six loop reactor with 2 turbines. However, EK analysed upgraded version of VVER-440 with 1485 MW_{th} and 500 MW_e while ARB analysed VVER-440 with 1375 MW_{th} and 440 MW_e
- 8 partners analysed PWR type reactors.
 - PWR-900 was analysed by IRSN and ENEA. This is a three-loop 2775 MW_{th} and 900 MW_e reactor.
 - PWR-1000 was analysed by TRACTEBEL, Bel V and CIEMAT. This is a three-loop 3000 MW_{th} reactor. The reactor modelled by CIEMAT has a slightly lower thermal power output of 2940.6 MW_{th}.
 - PWR-1300 was analysed by BOKU. This is a four-loop 3750 MW_{th} and 1300 MW_e reactor.
 - PWR Konvoi was analysed by HZDR. This is a four-loop 3950 MW_{th} and 1485 MW_e reactor.
 - EPR 3rd generation Pressurised Water Reactor analysed by VTT. This is a four-loop 4500 MW_{th} and 1660 MW_e power.
- 1 partner analysed a BWR reactor.

- BWR-4 was analysed by LEI. This is a 2381 MW_{th} reactor with a Mark I containment and two recirculation loops.

Some partners used generic reactor models and other partners used real plant configurations. This explains why some information is marked as being confidential.

2.2 Summary of selected scenarios

Hereunder a summary of the different performed simulations (and their associated scenarios) is represented. Firstly, for the LOCA and secondly for the SGTR:

2.2.1 LOCA scenarios at DBA and DEC-A conditions

For almost all reactor types LOCA simulations have been performed. In the framework of task 2.2 and in collaboration with the SEG it was decided that no common specific scenario will be used for all partners since the purpose of the project is not benchmarking. Therefore, all partners were free to use their own scenario.

Hereunder the most important data of the different LOCA-scenarios are listed.

- VVER LOCA scenarios:
 - For VVER-1000 LOCA scenarios, DBA and DEC-A conditions were modelled by ARB, SSTC-NRS, UJV-NRI and VTT. For DBA case, all partners assumed LB LOCA in cold leg, no operator actions, conservative initial and boundary conditions. However, partners used different assumptions for operation/availability of the safety systems. ARB decided additionally to analyse different sizes of the break. UJV-NRI provided analysis only for DBA conditions. For DEC-A conditions, in addition, ARB, SSTC-NRS and VTT decided to model the failure of the containment spray system.
 - The VVER-440 LOCA scenarios at DBA and DEC-A conditions were modelled by ARB and EK. ARB applied the same scenarios for DBA and DEC-A conditions as it is presented to VVER-1000. EK modelled only DBA conditions – guillotine break in the cold leg, no operator actions, conservative initial and boundary conditions, single failure: one hydro accumulator feeding into the reactor upper plenum, LPIS feeding into the broken leg is ignored.
- PWR LOCA scenarios:
 - DBA and DEC-A cases for PWR-900 were modelled by ENEA and IRSN. In the DBA scenario it was assumed a LB LOCA with a break of 16.3" in cold leg of loop 2 (without pressurizer) just downstream the primary pump; accident starts at nominal reactor power for ENEA case and with the reactor at 104% of nominal power in the IRSN case; LOOP (Loss-Of-Offsite Power) is assumed at scram signal combined with the single failure of one over two emergency diesel generators. For DEC-A conditions a LOCA with a break of 4" in the hot leg (at primary vessel outlet) of the loop 2 (without pressurizer) was chosen by partners. Accident starts at intermediate subcritical hot shutdown (reactor power approximately 1% of the nominal one and primary pressure 70 bar); accumulators not available; delayed safety injection system started by operator.
 - HZDR modelled LOCA scenario at DBA and DEC-A conditions for the PWR-Konvoi reactor. For both analyses it was assumed a double-ended guillotine break of cold leg loop 2 with the combination of a LOOP. For the DEC-A conditions additionally failures in ECCS were assumed. For both calculations conservative initial and boundary conditions were used.
 - VTT analysed LOCA for EPR-1600. The work was not performed in the frame of R2CA project. However, in this project is presented a summary of work that have been done before and its main results. A double-ended break in a cold leg was analysed.
- BWR LOCA scenarios for DEC-A conditions was analysed by LEI. For the scenario LB-LOCA, double-ended break of the main recirculation pipe for BWR-4 with delayed activation of LPCI system was assumed. Additionally, it was assumed that all ECCS, except LPCI, will not be available after the start of accident.

2.2.2 SGTR scenarios at DBA and DEC-A conditions

For all reactor types, SGTR simulations have been performed except for the BWR since these reactor types do not have steam generators. In the framework of task 2.2 and in collaboration with the SEG it was decided that no common specific scenario will be used for all partners since the purpose of the project is not benchmarking. Therefore, all partners were free to use their own scenarios.

- VVER SGTR scenarios:
 - For VVER-1000, the SGTR scenarios were modelled by ARB, BOKU, SSTC-NRS and UJV-NRI. ARB, for DBA case, assumed Steam Generator collector cover lift up (different diameters were analysed) and guillotine ruptures of SG tubes (it was assumed single, two and three ruptured tubes). SSTC-NRS also assumed Steam Generator collector cover lift up for Dn100 mm. Both partners used conservative initial and boundary conditions for the analysis. BOKU and UJV-NRI assumed single SG tube rupture for DBA analysis. In the case of the SGTR analysis using DEC-A conditions, ARB, BOKU and SSTC-NRS used additional failure - the emergency SG RV (BRU-A1) stuck open after its first opening. For DEC-A conditions, BOKU assumed another case - double ended guillotine break of a SG tube in loop 4 with simultaneous MSLB in a non-isolable part of the steam line inside the containment.
 - For VVER-440, SGTR scenarios were modelled by ARB and EK. ARB applied the same scenarios as those described above for the VVER-1000 SGTR scenario, for DBA and DEC-A conditions correspondingly. EK modelled only DBA conditions – steam generator collector cover lift up together with 3 SG tube break.
- PWR SGTR scenarios:
 - PWR-900 SGTR scenarios at DBA conditions was modelled only by IRSN. Two cases were assumed for the analysis. For both cases, a double-ended break of 1 SG tube on loop 3 (without PRZ) was assumed. The difference in the cases is break location: case 1 top and case 2 bottom of the U-tubes bundle on the hot leg side. For both cases no operator actions were considered before 20 minutes and a single failure was assumed – by-pass atmospheric steam Relief Valve (RV) of one of the intact SGs blocked closed.
 - PWR – 1000 SGTR scenario was analysed by Bel V, CIEMAT and TRACTEBEL. For the DBA case all partners decided to analyse a single U-tube double-ended break at full power at the top of the longest U-tube. No operator actions were considered for 30 minutes and single failure - stuck open RV applied on the RV of the affected SG. In the case of DEC-A conditions CIEMAT and TRACTEBEL assumed 3 tubes, double-ended break at the bottom of the U-tube bundle on the cold leg side loop with PRZ (shortest tube) combined with MSLB outside containment and after MSIV in the case of CIEMAT (isolable MSLB). Bel V for DEC-A conditions assumed double-ended break at the bottom of the three shortest U-tubes combined with MSLB outside containment before MSIV.
 - PWR – 1300 SGTR scenarios at DBA and DEC-A conditions were modelled by BOKU. For the DBA conditions, double-ended break of 1 SG tube at top of the U-tubes bundle was assumed. For DEC-A conditions two cases were analysed. First case was a double-ended break of 1 SG tube at top of the bundle and SG SRV stuck open after first activation.

2.3 Summary of modelling methods and approaches

2.3.1 Modelling methods and approaches for LOCA scenarios

For the modelling of LOCA accident and for the evaluation of their radiological consequences, it is needed to consider many phenomena and processes which are taking place in the reactor core, main reactor cooling circuit and. These are mostly thermal hydraulic, thermo-mechanical and FP behaviour questions, which should be solved. However, to evaluate possible activities in the reactor cooling circuit, containment and environment it is needed to estimate the fission product release during accident and this product transfer from the burst fuel claddings to reactor cooling circuit, then to containment, and from there to the environment.

Different methodologies based on different modelling computer codes or process assessment methods were used by the R2CA partners for the simulation of the phenomena and processes occurring during LOCA accidents. R2CA partners indeed, based on their own experience, chose commonly used methods in their countries and existing modelling codes in order to simulate in an appropriate way their selected LOCA scenarios and to get main results of thermal hydraulic (core, primary circuit & containment) and fuel rod thermo-mechanical analysis as well as far as possible evaluation results of fission product release and transportation.

In general summarizing modelling approaches used by partners it is possible to distinguish 3 types:

1. The thermal hydraulic, thermo-mechanical analysis were provided. Fission product transport and behaviour in the primary circuit and containment (whose releases from fuel were evaluated from the thermo-mechanical analysis) were also provided by computer codes. For this analysis, partners used complex modelling (coupled) computer codes.
2. Detail thermal hydraulic and thermo-mechanical analyses were provided by computer codes. However, for the fission product release and behaviour it was made conservative assumptions.
3. The thermal hydraulic analysis was provided by modelling computer codes, but thermo-mechanical analysis was not provided. Instead of those conservative assumptions – i.e. release from the fuel to the primary circuit of the entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient- was made. Taken in to account this assumption, the fission product behaviour was then simulated using computer code.

Table 2 summarizes the main modelling computer codes and the approaches used for the analysis of the LOCA scenarios at DBA and DEC-A conditions. The parts marked in green colour are those that are planned to be changed in the work related with Task 2.5 by the involved partner. A summary of the improvements foreseen by R2CA project partners presented in Section 3.

Organization	Reactor type	T-H	T-M	FP transport and behaviour
ARB	VVER-440; VVER-1000;	ATHLET 3.2	Not performed.	COCOSYS 3.0 100% of FP release.
EK	VVER-440	ATHLET 1.1	FUROM-2.1.1 for fuel rod history. FRAPTRAN-2.0 modified by EK	CONTAIN and EK developed methodology. 100% of FP release.
SSTC-NRS	VVER-1000	RELAP5 Mod 3.2	Not performed.	MELCOR 2.2 100% of FP release.
UJV-NRI	VVER-1000	ATHLET 3.1	TRANSURANUS	COCOSYS 2.4v4 100% of FP release.
ENEA	PWR-900	ASTEC 2.2.b	ASTEC 2.2.b	ASTEC 2.2.b
HZDR	PWR-Konvoi	ATHLET-CD 3.2	ATHLET-CD 3.2	ATHLET-CD 3.2 - FP release from fuel. 100% of FP release to containment Theoretical FP release to environment.
IRSN	PWR-900;	ASTEC 2.2	ASTEC 2.2	ASTEC 2.2
VTT	EPR-1600 (DBA conditions)	GENFLO, APROS	FRAPCON, FRAPTRAN-GENFLO	Not performed.
	VVER-1000 (DEC-A conditions)	GENFLO, APROS	FRAPTRAN-GENFLO	Not performed
LEI	BWR-4	ASTEC 2.1.1.6	ASTEC 2.1.1.6	ASTEC 2.1.1.6

Table 2. Modelling tools and modelling approaches used by partners in the frame of T2.3 LOCA analysis at DBA and DEC-A conditions.

2.3.2 Modelling methods and approaches for SGTR scenarios

For the modelling of SGTR accident, it is needed to consider many phenomena and processes taking place in the reactor core (spiking), main reactor cooling circuit, affected SG, intact SGs, available ECCS. These are mostly thermal hydraulic questions which should be solved. For the low temperatures calculated in the SGTR transient, fuel failure could not be expected. To evaluate possible activities in the reactor cooling circuit, then in the affected SG and environment, it is needed to estimate fission product release during accident from leaking fuel rods and their transfer from the primary circuit, then to the affected SG, and from there to the environment. In general no simulations of clad primary defect formation are made because fuel failure could not be expected in the simulated scenarios.

There are different methodologies used with different modelling computer codes or process assessment methods for the evaluation of the phenomena and processes during SGTR accident. R2CA project partners, based on their experience, have chosen methods and modelling codes in order simulate appropriate SGTR scenarios and to get main results of thermal hydraulic analysis as well as evaluation of fission product release and transportation. Table 3, summarizes the main modelling computer codes and approaches used for the analysis of the SGTR scenario at DBA and DEC-A conditions. The parts marked in green colour are those that are planned to be changed for the analyses associated with Task 2.5.

Organization	Type of reactor	T-H	FP transport and behaviour
ARB	VVER-440; VVER-1000	ATHLET 3.2	COCOSYS
EK	VVER-440	RELAP5 Mod 3.3	RING
SSTC-NRS	VVER-1000	RELAP5 Mod 3.2	Not performed. Assumed 100% release of FP from primary circuit to environment
UJV-NRI	VVER-1000	ATHLET 3.1	Conservative and simplified methodology developed by UJV-NRI
BOKU	VVER-1000; PWR1300	RELAP5-3D 4.0.3	Not performed. Limitation of RELAP5-3D 4.0.3 (the transport of fission products can only be conducted in the liquid phase)
TRACTEBEL	PWR-1000	RELAPmod2.5 (for DBA case) MELCOR2.2 (for DEC-A case)	RELAPmod2.5 (for DBA case) MELCOR2.2 (for DEC-A case)
Bel V	PWR-1000	CATHARE2/V2.5_3/mod8.1	VBA-script
IRSN	PWR-900;	ASTEC 2.2	ASTEC 2.2
CIEMAT	PWR-1000	MELCOR2.2	MELCOR2.2

Table 3. Modelling tools and modelling approaches used by partners in the frame of T2.3 SGTR analysis at DBA and DEC-A conditions.

2.4 Main results from LOCA calculations

In this chapter, a summary of individually prepared reports provided by partners is presented. Reports were prepared according to the template (Annex A1) which was earlier discussed among project partners. Individual reports contain a big amount of information. However, this summary is focused on the main results of the thermal

hydraulic and thermo-mechanic analysis as well as activity in the environment as the main parameter, which directly influences the evaluation of radiological consequences.

VVER-440 DBA case. Calculations were provided by ARB and EK.

- ARB studied several scenarios for DBA case: double-ended guillotine break and leak from the 250 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter break in the cold leg. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 1050 °C. For the LOCA analysis of the 250 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter breaks maximal cladding outer surface temperatures are significant lower and do not reach 400 °C.

At this stage of study, ARB did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, regarding fission product behaviour they assumed a release from all the fuel rods of their entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient. This is a very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. ARB calculated $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{15}$ Bq integral activity released into the environment during the first 80000 s after the start of accident for the double-ended guillotine break scenario. The analysis, assuming different diameters of the LOCA: 250 mm, 100 mm, and 50 mm, showed that integral activity released into the environment, during the first 60000 s after the start of accident, was $\sim 2.1 \times 10^{14}$ Bq, $\sim 2.7 \times 10^{14}$ Bq and 1.3×10^{14} Bq respectively. This calculation results showed peculiarities of the accident in the containment for large and medium leaks of the primary circuit. The containment pressure for medium leaks is maintained longer due to the nature of the bubble-vacuum system and this causes the bigger activity in environment.

- EK studied one scenario for DBA case: guillotine break in the cold leg, no operator actions, conservative initial and boundary conditions. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 900 °C. The thermo-mechanical analysis provided by EK showed that there is no burst of fuel cladding, but only clad ballooning. Even though thermo-mechanical analysis did not show fuel cladding damage EK assumed the release from the fuel of the entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient. In addition to the mentioned assumption, FP from the fuel was assumed to be released to the primary coolant instantaneously due to the fragmentation of the fuel. This is a very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. EK calculated the integral activity released into the environment equal to $\sim 9.5 \times 10^{13}$ Bq.

VVER-440 DEC-A case. Calculations were provided by ARB.

- ARB used similar approach and assumptions as for the DBA studies. Additionally, unlike LOCA DBA, for DEC-A conditions additional failures were considered (i.e. failure of the containment spray system). However, the reactor power were considered at 100% (as it was 104% for DBA case). ARB provided (several scenarios): double-ended guillotine break and various leak diameters from 250 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter break in the cold leg. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reaches ~ 720 °C. For the LOCA analysis of the 250 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures are significantly lower and do not reach ~ 400 °C.

At this stage of study, ARB did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour, partner assumed the release from the fuel of the entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient. This is a very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. ARB calculated $\sim 2.8 \times 10^{14}$ Bq of integral activity released into the environment during the first 60000 s after the start of accident for the double-ended guillotine break scenario. ARB also provided analysis assuming different diameter of the LOCA: 250 mm, 100 mm, and 50 mm. The integral activity released into environment during the first 60000 s after the start of accident was $\sim 3.1 \times 10^{14}$ Bq, $\sim 2.4 \times 10^{14}$ Bq and 1.3×10^{14} Bq respectively.

VVER-1000 DBA case. Calculations were provided by ARB, SSTC-NRS and UJV-NRI.

- As with VVER-440 type reactor case, ARB studied several scenarios for DBA conditions: double-ended guillotine break and leak from the 350 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter breaks in the cold leg. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 1100 °C (for the highest power fuel rod) and ~950 °C (for the highest power fuel assembly). For the LOCA analysis of the 350 mm diameter break maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reached ~810 °C. In the cases of the 100 mm and 50 mm diameter break maximal cladding outer surface temperatures are significantly lower ~360 °C.

At this stage of study, ARB did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour, they assumed that the entire contents of the gas gap were released at the beginning of the transient. This is very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. ARB calculated the integral activity released into the environment equals to ~5.5e+11 Bq, during the first 1400 s after the start of accident for the double-ended guillotine break scenario. ARB also provided released activities in the environment assuming different break diameters: 350 mm, 100 mm, and 50 mm. The integral activity released into the environment during the first 1400 s after the start of accident was ~5.3e+11 Bq, ~5.7e+11 Bq and 3.7e+11 Bq respectively.

- SSTC-NRS studied one scenario: LOCA with instantaneous double-ended guillotine break of a cold leg near the reactor cold nozzles. Additionally, the loss of normal power supply is postulated at the moment of IE occurrence. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 880 °C.

At this stage of study, SSTC-NRS did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour, they assumed, as ARB, that the entire contents of the gas gap was released at the beginning of the transient. This is very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. The integral activity released into the environment during the first 60000s after the accident is ~1.6e+13 Bq.

- UJV-NRI studied one scenario: LOCA with instantaneous double-ended guillotine break of a cold leg of RCS loop near the reactor vessel. The initial and boundary conditions are set conservatively towards maximum mass release from the containment. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~860°C.

UJV-NRI performed fuel thermo-mechanical calculations indicating that no fuel rod failure occurs. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour they assumed that the entire contents of the gas gap were released from 30 to 1800 s after the initiating event. This is very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related T2.5. The integral activity only of the isotopes with high conversion factor released into the environment during the first 60000s after the accident is ~3.5e+11 Bq.

VVER-1000 DEC-A case. Calculations were provided by ARB, SSTC-NRS and VTT.

- Like for the VVER-1000 type reactor ARB studied several scenarios for DEC-A case: double-ended guillotine break and leak from 350 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter breaks in the cold leg. For DEC-A conditions, in addition, it was decided to model the failure of the containment spray system. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 890°C (for the highest power fuel rod) and ~850 °C (for the highest power fuel assembly). For the LOCA analysis of the 350 mm, 100 mm and 50 mm diameter break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures are significant lower ~ 350°C.

ARB at this stage of study did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour they assumed that the entire contents of the gas gap were released at the beginning of the transient. This is very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the

work related to Task 2.5. The integral activity released into the environment equals to $\sim 12.5 \times 10^{11}$ Bq, during the first 1800 s after the start of accident for the double-ended guillotine break scenario. ARB provided the analysis assuming different diameter of the LOCA: 350 mm, 100 mm, and 50 mm. The integral activity released into the environment during the first 3000 s after the start of accident was $\sim 17.1 \times 10^{11}$ Bq, $\sim 16.0 \times 10^{11}$ Bq and $\sim 9.8 \times 10^{11}$ Bq respectively.

- SSTC-NRS studied one scenario: LOCA with instantaneous double-ended guillotine break of a cold leg near the reactor cold nozzles. Additionally, the loss of normal power supply is postulated at the moment of IE occurrence. In addition, for the DEC-A conditions it was decided to model the failure of the containment spray system. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that in the case of the double-ended guillotine break, the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 900 °C.
At this stage of study, SSTC-NRS did not perform thermal-mechanical analysis. However, for the analysis of fission product behaviour, partner assumed the release from the fuel of the entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient. This is a very conservative assumption, and it is planned to be changed in the work related to Task 2.5. The integral activity released into the environment during the first 60000s after the accident is $\sim 4.6 \times 10^{13}$ Bq.
- VTT studied one scenario: double-ended break in cold leg. The core power was set to 104 %. VTT model does not include neither the containment, nor its spray system. This corresponds to a DEC-A case scenario, where the failure of a spray system is considered. Containment was not modelled also because in this scenario no core damage was expected. The calculation results of the thermal hydraulic analysis show that maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 890 °C and according to the VTT's results of thermo-mechanical analysis - there is no damage of fuel cladding in the case of analysed LOCA for DEC-A case.
Analysis of fission product behaviour was not provided at this stage of study. Improvements for thermo-mechanical analysis together with FP transport and behaviour processes is planned to Task 2.5.

In case of LOCA analysis 3 types of the PWR reactor (PWR-900, PWR-Konvoi and EPR-1600) were analyzed by 4 partners (ENEA, HZDR, IRSN and VTT).

PWR-900 DBA case. Calculations were provided by ENEA and IRSN.

- ENEA used generic model of PWR-900 with a thermal power of 2775 MW. ENEA studied one DBA case scenario and provided additional sensitivity analysis to quantify the effect of some user dependent parameters and/or assumed boundary conditions on the predicted number of failed rods. In this scenario it was assumed a LOCA with a break of 16.3" in cold leg of loop 2 (without pressurizer) just downstream the primary pump. Accident starts at nominal reactor power. LOOP is assumed at SCRAM signal combined with the single failure of one over two emergency diesel generators. The thermal hydraulic analysis showed maximal cladding outer surface temperature ~ 860 °C. The thermo mechanical analysis indicated cladding failure of one of the five groups of FAs modelled. This corresponds to the failure of 20 FA on a total of 157 FA and these accounts for approximately 12.7% of the total number of rods. ENEA calculated $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{12}$ Bq integral activity released into the environment during the first 180000 s (50 h) after the start of accident. Performed sensitivity analysis pointed out a non-negligible effect of cladding failure criterion on the prediction of the number of failed rods. Depending on user choices, the number of failed rods can range from 0 to the 38.9% of the total number of rods.
- IRSN studied 1 DBA reference case scenario and provided additional sensitivity analysis calculation on clad failures. DBA scenario: LOCA with a break of 16.3" in cold leg just downstream the primary pump. Accident starts at 104% of nominal reactor power. LOOP is assumed at SCRAM signal combined with the single failure of one over two emergency diesel generators. IRSN provided thermal hydraulic analysis indicating that maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach ~ 750 °C. The thermo-mechanical

analysis showed cladding failure of two of the five groups of FAs modelled. The total number of failed rods thus accounts for approximately 33.1% of the total number of rods. IRSN calculated $\sim 3.5 \times 10^{13}$ Bq integral activity released into the environment during the first 180000 s (50 h) after the start of accident. Additionally, several parameters have been identified as playing a role in the burst clad during the scenario. Some sensitivity calculations were performed to evaluate their impact on fuel rod failures and then on source term prediction. Results of performed analysis showed that, in some cases using different parameters it is possible to reach a situation with lower amount of fuel rod failures (failure of one cladding group instead of two).

PWR-900 DEC-A case. Calculations were provided by ENEA and IRSN.

- ENEA used generic model of PWR-900 with a thermal power of 2775 MW. ENEA studied one DEC-A case scenario. In this scenario a LOCA with a break of 4" in the hot leg (at primary vessel outlet) of the loop 2 (without pressurizer) was chosen. Accident starts at intermediate subcritical hot shutdown (reactor power approximately 1% of the nominal one and primary pressure 70 bar); accumulators are not available; safety injection system started by operator 36.5 minutes after the start of the accident. The thermal hydraulic analysis showed the maximal cladding outer surface temperature $\sim 2250^\circ\text{C}$. However, this high temperature was reached only in one of the five groups of FAs modelled. Other groups did not reach 1250°C . The analysis performed by ENEA indicated cladding failure of four of the five groups of FAs modelled. This corresponds to the failure of 105 FA on a total of 157 FA and it accounts for approximately 70% of the total number of rods. ENEA calculated $\sim 8.7 \times 10^{13}$ Bq integral activity released into the environment during the first 172800 s (48 h) after the start of accident.
- IRSN studied 1 DEC-A case scenario. The initiator for this scenario is a 4" break on the hot leg 2 (without pressurizer) at primary vessel outlet. IRSN provided thermal hydraulic analysis indicated that maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reach $\sim 1000^\circ\text{C}$. The analysis performed by IRSN indicated cladding failure of four of the five modelled groups of FAs. This corresponds to the failure of 105 FA on a total of 157 FA and it accounts for approximately 70% of the total number of rods. IRSN calculated $\sim 1.4 \times 10^{14}$ Bq integral activity into the environment during the first 180000 s (~ 50 h) after the start of accident.

PWR-Konvoi DBA case. Calculations were provided by HZDR.

- For the DBA analysis, a double-ended guillotine break in cold leg loop 2 was assumed in combination of a loss-of-offsite power. For the calculations, conservative initial and boundary conditions were used. The thermal hydraulic analysis showed that the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reached $\sim 1050^\circ\text{C}$. Thermo-mechanical analysis showed that cladding ruptures are calculated in core section #1, which represents the hot rods of the core (10 % of all fuel rods located in active core). The analysis only takes the release from fuel rods into account. The transport of fission products from the RPV to the containment is not calculated. Conservatively, it was assumed that all the released fission products are transported immediately to the containment (without any retention in the primary circuit) and are homogeneously distributed within the containment. Therefore, the pressure in containment is not calculated. To provide a release rate value, a conservative assumption is made. It was assumed the highest possible release rate at highest possible containment pressure (containment design pressure). Furthermore, the decay of FP is also not considered for that conservative estimation. Total activity of FP (Xe, Kr, I and Cs) at the end of ATHLET-CD simulation (600 s after beginning of LBLOCA) is 2.32×10^{17} Bq. Taken into account above mentioned conservative assumptions and design leakage rate (0.25 % of volume/day) the HZDR calculated $\sim 5.84 \times 10^{14}$ Bq integral activity into the environment during the first 86400 s (24h) after the start of accident.

PWR-Konvoi DEC-A case. Calculations were provided by HZDR.

- For DEC-A analysis case, a double-ended guillotine break of cold leg loop 2 was assumed in combination of a loss-of-offsite power and with an additional a failure in ECCS. For the calculations, conservative initial

and boundary conditions were used (same as for DBA). The thermal hydraulic analysis showed that the maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reached ~ 1160 °C. The Thermo-mechanical analysis showed that the cladding rupture is calculated in core section 1, which represents the hot rods of the core (10 % of all fuel rods located in active core). Thus, the result of thermo-mechanical analysis is the same at DBA case. Provided analysis only takes the FP from fuel rods into account (same conservative assumption as for DBA). Because it was assumed the same conservative assumptions of FP transfer and behaviour like in the DBA – the calculated integral activity into the environment during the first 86400 s (24h) after the start of accident is the same $\sim 5.84e+14$ Bq.

EPR-1600 DBA case. Calculations were provided by VTT.

- The LOCA analysis for EPR-1600 provided by VTT. Though the calculations were not performed in the frame of R2CA project, a summary of the work done before is presented here. A double-ended break in a cold leg was assumed. The thermal hydraulic analysis showed that maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reached ~ 900 °C (using FRAPTRAN-GENFLO simulations). Thermo-mechanical calculation results showed that in the worst case, 1.4% of all core fuel rods could burst. There is no transient FP model for LOCA, the only available model is for reactivity-initiated accidents..

BWR DEC-A case. Calculations were provided by LEI.

- For the analysis, the LB-LOCA scenario was considered. A double-ended break of the main recirculation pipe for BWR-4 was assumed with a delayed activation of LPCI system. In this analysis case, other ECCS systems were not available after the start of accident and no operator action was taken into account. Results of the thermal hydraulic analysis showed that maximal cladding outer surface temperatures reached ~ 830 °C after full core uncover. Thermo-mechanics analysis indicated cladding failure of two of the four modelled groups of FAs. This corresponds to the failure of 320 FA on a total of 548 FA. In total $\sim 55\%$ of all active zone was calculated to fail in analysed scenario. Flow path of fission products from the containment to environment were considered only through the containment design leakages. The calculated integral activity into the environment is $5.3e+14$ Bq during the first $2e+5$ s after the start of accident.

2.5 Main results from SGTR calculations

In this chapter a summary of individually prepared reports provided by partners is presented. Reports were prepared according to the template (Annex A2) which was earlier discussed among project partners. Individual reports contain a big amount of information. However, this summary focuses on the main results of the thermal hydraulic and FP transport and behaviour as well as activity in the environment as the main parameter, which directly influences the evaluation of radiological consequences.

VVER-440 DBA case. Calculations were provided by ARB and EK.

- ARB studied several scenarios for DBA case: Steam generator collector cover lift-up (leak size – 107 mm, 60 mm, 40 mm, 20 mm) and guillotine rupture of 1, 2 or 3 SG tube (s). The calculation results show that the mass of the coolant flowing through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit for different scenarios varies from approximately 75 to 470 ton (in 2500s to 18000s). ARB calculated that the primary circuit activity including spiking equals $4.6e+13$ Bq.

The presence of a postulated single failure (failure to close of control SG SV of affected SG after its opening) strongly increases the release from the affected SG to the environment and leads to the unhindered outflow of the primary coolant and its mixture with the boiler water of the SG to the environment. The release from the affected SG to the environment through the failed control SG SV for different scenarios varies from approx. 40 to above 440 t. Considering the conservative assumptions (the deposition and dilution of isotopes in the primary and secondary sides, including the affected SG, is not considered), this leads to a release into the environment equal to approximately $2e+13$ to $4.6e+13$ Bq.

- EK studied 2 scenarios for DBA case: Steam generator collector cover lift-up and 3 SG broken tubes. The two scenarios started with the break of three SG tubes and with the opening of collector cover, respectively. The primary pressure decreased to the secondary pressure. It took 4000 s in case of tube rupture and 2000 s for collector cover opening. The breakflow started with 50 kg/s flowrate for the SG tube break event, while the initial breakflow was about 100 kg/s for the collector cover opening. The lost coolant was compensated by the operation of HPIS. At the end of the simulation both scenarios reached stable conditions with equal pressures in the primary and secondary circuits. EK calculated the activity in the primary coolant (including iodine spiking) which equals $9.34e+14$ Bq.

VVER-440 DEC A case. Calculations were provided by ARB.

- For DEC A case, ARB added another failure on BRU-A1 (Steam dump valve to-atmosphere stuck open) to the studied DBA scenarios. The calculation results show that the mass of the coolant flowing through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit for different scenarios varies from approximately 75 to 470 ton (in 5000s to 16000s). ARB calculated that the primary circuit activity including spiking equals $4.6e+13$ Bq.

The Presence of a postulated single failure (failure to close of control SG SV of affected SG after its opening) and additional failure (failure to close BRU-A1) strongly increases the release from the affected SG to the environment and leads to the unhindered outflow of the primary coolant and its mixture with the boiler water of the SG to the environment. The release from the affected SG to the environment through the failed control SG SV and BRU-A1 for different scenarios varies from approx. 60 to above 450 t. In contrast to the SGTR DBA, the presence of an additional failure to close the BRU-A1 leads to an increase in the activity release rate into the environment, the minimum time of the maximum activity release is reduced to 33% of the DBA value.

VVER-1000 DBA case. Calculations were provided by ARB, SSTC-NRS, BOKU and UJV-NRI.

- ARB studied several scenarios for DBA case: Steam generator collector cover lift-up (leak size – 100 mm, 60 mm, 40 mm, 20 mm) and guillotine rupture of 1, 2 or 3 SG tube (s). The calculation results show that the mass of the coolant flowing through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit for different scenarios varies from approximately 40 to 810 t.

The presence of a postulated single failure (failure to close of BRU-A of affected SG after its opening) strongly increases the release from the affected SG to the environment and leads to the unhindered outflow of the primary coolant and its mixture with the boiler water of the SG to the environment. The release from the affected SG to the environment through the failed BRU-A for different scenarios varies from approx. 90 to above 760 t. Taking into account the conservative assumptions (the deposition and dilution of isotopes in the primary and secondary sides, including the affected SG, is not considered), this leads to the integral release into the environment which equals approximately $4e+13$ to $2.4e+14$ Bq.

- SSTC NRS studied one scenario for DBA case: The SG-1 cold collector cover lift-up is assumed. This results in a primary to secondary break of 100mm diameter. Because of operator response delays and since the opening setpoints of SG safety relief valves (SG SRV) and of steam dump valves (BRU-A) are lower than the head of the HPIS pumps injecting into primary circuit, the initiating event results in release of radioactive primary coolant to the environment. The break mass flow rate at the very beginning of accident reaches its maximum value. Loss of coolant causes sharp decrease in primary pressure and coolant boiling in the vessel upper part. The loss of normal power supply is postulated at the beginning of IE and leads to Diesel Generator start-up. The single failure is assumed on Diesel Generator-1 leading to corresponding failures of 1/3 HPIS and 1/3 LPIS. After closure of turbine stop valves the steam dump to atmosphere valves BRU-As open at 2 s on all SGs. At the same time the short-term opening of control SG SRV is observed. SI is activated at 35 s followed by HPIS-1, 2 trains injection. Because of the break flow the secondary side of broken SG-1 is completely filled with water at 350 s and water release through

BRU-A into environment begins. 15 minutes after IE occurrence the forced closure of the feed water valves and BRU-A of broken SG by operator is modelled that temporarily terminates the release, but HPIS operation and coolant heat-up causes an increase of RCS pressure and at 1350 s periodic opening of control SG SRV of broken SG begins. At 1800 s of the accident the operator actions on termination of HPIS operation, closure of all main steam isolation valves and switching of BRU-As of intact SGs into cool-down mode are modelled. This eventually causes gradual decrease of RCS and broken SG pressure. By 2500 s the last opening cycle of SG-1 SRV occurs, and leak flow decreases to zero. From that time the break is isolated. The total mass loss from the primary circuit to the broken SG secondary side is 210 ton. The maximum fuel cladding temperature of 351°C is reached at the beginning of the Initiating Event. No challenge to the cooling of the fuel cladding is observed in the accident. The integral activity released into the environment is calculated conservatively assuming release of total primary circuit coolant activity to the environment taking into account the iodine spike and is equal to about 7.79e+13Bq.

- UJV-NRI studied one scenario for DBA case: Guillotine rupture of a single steam generator tube is assumed. The single failure is assumed on the Steam Dump to Atmosphere (BRU-A) of the affected SG (BRU-A stuck open). The pressure in the secondary circuit rises at initiator due to the turbine trip valves. At the same time the reactor is shutdown and remaining BRU-A are opened. The pressure then decreases significantly, mainly for the affected SG. In general, the temperature decreases throughout the accident. The water mass in affected SG drops significantly due to closure of the feedwater line. In the later phase, the water mass rises thanks to the leak from the primary circuit and the SG becomes flooded. Thanks to the activation of safety injection systems and reactor SCRAM, the primary circuit remains subcooled throughout the accident. The calculation results show that the mass of the coolant flowing through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit is approximately about 260 t (in 22000 s). The fission products release starts when the BRU-A open. The dominant way is through the BRU-A4, which belongs to the affected SG and remains opened throughout the accident. UJV-NRI calculated activity in the primary coolant equals 5.99e+15 Bq. The integral activity only of the isotopes with high conversion factor (Br-83, Rb-88, Sr-90, I-131, Cs-137, Xe-133) released into the environment is ~2.23e+15 Bq. The current approach is overly conservative, e.g. not taking into account the radioactive decay. Simplifications introduced in the fission product transport calculation may lead to significant overestimation of released activity. Improvement of this approach is planned within the WP4.
- BOKU studied one scenario for DBA case: A hot header break is assumed, this means a leakage (1.4% - equivalent diameter of 100 mm) from the primary to the secondary side of the reactor occurs in loop No. 2. This constitutes a primary to secondary system leak (PRISE). Due to the closing of the turbine stop valve the emergency power mode is initiated. It is assumed that one diesel generator (DG) is defect (single failure case). Therefore, all active safety systems of one loop (HPIS, LPIS, Auxiliary Feedwater) are not available. Operator actions are the depressurization of the secondary side (60 K/h) via the BRU-A valves in the intact loops and the deactivation of the HPIS after 1800s to limit the loss of coolant through the break. During the first seconds of the accident, the break mass flow rate reaches its maximum value of 500 kg/s. Due to the SCRAM and the pressure reduction at the Primary System, the mass flow rate through the break decreases rapidly until 400s. After the activation of the HPIS the break mass flow rate stabilizes at about 100 kg/s. After 1900s, the HPIS are stopped and the break mass flow rate decreases. Due to the activation of the Accumulators the break mass flow rate is shortly increased again. At 2000s the flow through the break is reversed for about 2000s. As the MSIV closes, the pressure in SG 2 deviates in comparison to the unaffected loops. Between 300s and 1900s the PS – pressure and the pressure in SG 2 are affected by the opening/closure of the BRU-A in the isolated SG.. The HPIS and the Accumulators are very important in this accident. Those systems prevent a dry out of the core. The HPIS is switched on automatically and is deactivated by the operator at 1900s. The LPIS are activated at about 6000s, when the pressure threshold of 25 bar abs in the primary side is reached. During the transient the core is never at risk of running empty due to the injection of the HPIS, the Accumulators and later the LPIS. The PRZ runs empty early in the transient and is filled up again at about 3000s due to the HPIS and Accumulators injection, as well as the reverse mass flow rate through the break. It was assumed that

I131 is released in the core within the first 300s of the transient. Fission products can only reach the environment through the BRU-A valve in the affected loop. The maximum I131 concentration reached in the primary system is $2.5e+13$ Bq at about 400s after transient initiation. The released activity to the environment is not evaluated because of the limitation of RELAP5-3D: the transport of fission products can only be conducted in the liquid phase. BOKU will search for a solution of this problem.

VVER-1000 DEC A case. Calculations were provided by ARB, SSTC-NRS and BOKU.

- ARB studied several scenarios for DEC A case: Steam generator collector cover lift-up (leak size – 100 mm, 60 mm, 40 mm, 20 mm) and Guillotine rupture of 1, 2 or 3 SG tube (s). The calculation results show that the mass of the coolant flowing through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit for different scenarios varies from approximately 40 to 900 t.

The presence of failures to close of BRU-A and control SG SV of affected SG after their opening increases the release from the affected SG to the environment and leads to the unhindered outflow of the primary coolant and its mixture with the boiler water of the SG to the environment. The release from the affected SG to the environment through the failed BRU-A and control SG SV for different scenarios varies from approx. 90 to above 850 t. In contrast to the SGTR DBA, the presence of an additional failure to close the control SG SV leads to an increase in the activity release rate into the environment, the minimum time of the maximum activity release is reduced to 13% of the DBA value.

- SSTC NRS studied one scenario for DEC A case: The SG-1 cold collector cover lift-up is assumed. This results in a primary to secondary break of 100mm diameter. Because of operator response delays and since the opening setpoints of SG safety relief valves (SG SRV) and of steam dump valves (BRU-A) are lower than the head of the HPIS pumps injecting into primary circuit, the initiating event results in release of radioactive primary coolant to the environment. In DEC-A scenario an additional failure of SG-1 BRU-A is postulated assuming that this valve stuck in open position after the first opening. The break mass flow rate at the very beginning of accident reaches its maximum value. Loss of coolant causes sharp decrease in primary pressure and coolant boiling in the reactor core. The loss of normal power supply is postulated at the beginning of IE and leads to Diesel Generator startup. The single failure is assumed on Diesel Generator-1 leading to corresponding failure of 1/3 HPIS (High pressure Injection System) and 1/3 LPIS (Low Pressure Injection System). After closure of turbine stop valves the steam dump to atmosphere valves BRU-As open at 2 s on all SGs. The BRU-A valve at SG-1 is stuck open according to calculation scenario. SI is activated at 35 s followed by HPIS-1,2 trains injection. Rapid decrease of RCS pressure down to LPIS shut-off head (24 bar) causes start of LPIS injection to the primary circuit at 610 s. Because of the primary-to-secondary break flow the secondary side of broken SG-1 is completely filled with water at 850 s and water release through stuck BRU-A to environment begins. 15 minutes after IE occurrence the operator actions on broken SG feedwater lines isolation, termination of injection from 1 out of 2 operating HPIS pumps, closure of all main steam isolation valves, switching of BRU-As of intact SGs into cool-down mode, and opening of gas removal valves from PRZ top are modelled. The latter causes an increase of PRZ level and at 1260 s (when PRZ level reaches 8 m and coolant subcooling is greater than 10°C) the operator switches off LPIS pumps. 30 min after IE start operator aligns RCS residual heat removal system. At 4100 s the sump water is completely exhausted and injection from the last operating HPIS stops. Close to 8000 s the leak rate stabilizes around zero value. The maximum fuel cladding temperature of $\sim 340^{\circ}\text{C}$ is reached at the beginning of the Initiating Event. No challenge to the cooling of the fuel cladding is observed in the accident. The integral activity released into the environment is calculated conservatively assuming release of total primary circuit coolant activity to the environment taking into account the iodine spike and is equal to approximately $7.79e+13$ Bq. The used approach assumes conservatively that all RCS coolant activity is released to the environment.
- BOKU studied two scenarios for DEC A. In the first scenario the initiating event of is a double-ended break of one SG tube with an equivalent break area of 13 mm^2 (2 times). This allows coolant of the Primary System to reach the Secondary System. In addition, a simultaneous guillotine break of the main steam

line with an equivalent break area of 0.283 m² occurs. Failure of all HPIS trains and Hydro - accumulators is assumed, while the LPIS is available. Operator actions are the depressurization of the secondary side (60 K/h) via the BRU-A valves in the intact loops and the opening of the power operated relief valve (PORV) after 1800s. During the first seconds of the accident the break mass flow rate reaches its maximum value of 24 kg/s. Due to the SCRAM and the pressure reduction at the Primary System, the mass flow rate through the break decreases slowly until 1800s. At 1800s, the secondary side cooling via the BRU-A valves is initiated. After the LPIS is activated the primary inventory and the primary mass flow rate is increased considerably, which leads to an increase of the mass flow through the break at about 5700s. The maximum value (about 1900 kg/s) of the mass flow in the main steam line is reached within the first 100s. The Primary mass inventory is reduced in the first 5100s of the transient due to the loss of coolant through the primary break. The level of the PRZ decreases due to the SCRAM and the depressurization of the Primary System, until it is empty at about 1000s. After 1800s the PRZ level begins to fill in again, when the depressurization of the secondary system is initiated. This is caused by the boiler-condenser phenomenon where steam flow of the Primary System is redirected to the PRZ. In accordance with the decline of the primary mass inventory, the PRZ level starts to decrease again after 2500s. This development is reversed after 5100s when the LPIS is activated and starts injecting into the Primary System. The operator initiates the opening of the PRZ PORV at 1800s. This leads to an increase in the pressure drop at the Primary System. The simultaneous depressurization of the secondary side enhances this effect. At about 5600s the PORV reacts to the injection of the LPIS and a greater amount of coolant is ejected. The BRU-A valves of the intact loops are opened by the operator at 1800s. This action is primarily intended to depressurize the secondary side, which eventually results in a decrease of the primary side pressure. Within 300s after the SCRAM, an iodine spike is developed which is caused by the fast loss of reactor power that is associated with a pressure decrease. The I131 activity released into the environment through the MSLB is highly dependent on the breakflow of the SGTR (PRISE). It is expected that the whole iodine concentration, which reaches the secondary side is ejected through the MSLB into the environment. However, I131 only reaches an activity of 3e+8, which is caused by a limitation of RELAP5-3D as the transport of fission products can only be conducted in the liquid phase. There is not enough liquid available in the affected SG to transport the iodine. Therefore, most of the iodine, which is transported to the SS, accumulates at the bottom of the SG. BOKU will search for a solution of this problem.

In the second scenario a hot header break is assumed, this means a leakage (1.4% - equivalent diameter of 100 mm) from the primary to the secondary side of the reactor occurs in loop No. 4. This constitutes a primary to secondary system leak (PRISE). It is assumed that the BRU-A valve in the affected loop is stuck in an open position after the first opening. Due to the closing of the turbine valve the emergency power mode is initiated. It is assumed that all HPIS and ACCs are available, but the LPIS cannot be used. Operator actions are the depressurization of the secondary side (60 K/h) via the BRU-A valves in the intact loops and the deactivation of the HPIS/ACCs after 1800s to limit the loss of coolant through the break. During the first seconds of the accident the break mass flow rate reaches its maximum value of 450 kg/s. Due to the SCRAM and the pressure reduction at the Primary System, the mass flow rate through the break decreases rapidly until 200s. After the activation of the HPIS and the ACCs the break mass flow rate stabilizes again but decreases steadily until 1800s. After 1800s, the HPIS are stopped and the break mass flow rate gets negative for a short time until it steadies at about 40 kg/s. As the MSIV close, the pressure in SG 4 deviates in comparison to the unaffected loops. The pressure in the affected SG is reduced rapidly due to the break. The three intact SGs display a pressure increase in the first phase of the transient, because they have to take on a higher load. Depressurization of the intact SGs starts only when the BRU-A valves are activated by the operator after 1800s. The HPIS and the Accumulators are very important in this accident. Those systems prevent a dry out of the core. The HPIS is switched on automatically due to the pressure threshold and is deactivated by the operator at 1800s. The PRZ runs empty early in the transient. Fission products can only reach the environment through the BRU-A valve in the affected loop. The I131 integral activity released into the environment is about 1.0e+13 Bq. The maximum I131 concentration reached in the Primary Side is ~1.3e+13 at about 400s after transient

initiation. The released activity to the environment is not evaluated because of the limitation of RELAP5-3D (mentioned above in the first scenario).

PWR-900 DBA case. Calculations were provided by IRSN.

- IRSN studied 2 scenarios for DBA case: A double-ended break of one U-tube at the top / the bottom of the U-bundle of SG 3 (close to the hot water box) is postulated to occur. The only difference between the 2 simulated scenarios DBA1 and DBA2 is the location of the break (at the top of the U-tube bundle for the scenario DBA1/at the bottom for the scenario DBA2). For both scenarios, it is assumed that the RV of SG2 (one of the 2 intact SGs) is blocked closed to penalize the cooling of the primary circuit by the intact SGs. It is also assumed that no operator actions occur during 20 minutes from the reactor SCRAM. At transient initiation ($t=0.0s$), the calculated SG break mass flow rate is about 42kg/s in the scenario DBA1 (35kg/s for DBA2). Despite the automatic actions aiming at maintaining the pressurizer level and pressure, both continue to decrease. This eventually leads to the isolation of the pressurizer heaters and letdown (at PRZ level of 14%). Due to the increase of the secondary pressure SG1 and 3, RVs opens (steam discharge at a setpoint of 71 bar abs) starting the releases to the atmosphere. The primary circuit depressurization continues: the reactor is tripped on low PRZ pressure (131 bar abs) and the HPIS is started on very low PRZ pressure (119.3 bar abs). The very low PRZ pressure signal (119.3 bar abs) will also stop the main feedwater and start the auxiliary feedwater. Due to the HPIS, the primary pressure and the break mass flow are slightly increased. On the secondary side, the secondary pressure is stabilized around the setpoint of the SGs RVs (71 bar abs). The operator actions are initiated 20 minutes after the reactor SCRAM. The affected SG3 is isolated by closing the main steam isolation valve and stopping the blow-down and the auxiliary feedwater. The two HPSI pumps are successively stopped by the operator once the respective saturation criteria are fulfilled. After the second HPSI stop, the operator is guided by various emergency operating procedures (REF 28°C/h, ECP3, ECP2,...) that trigger automatic actions (spray activation, opening of SG1 RV, start of make-up (charge) circuit) depending on thermal hydraulics conditions and mainly the primary pressure evolution. Once the primary and secondary pressures are balanced in the affected SG, the break flow is ended. During the transient, the core cooling is ensured (no core uncover). The subcooling of the core and the upper plenum is also maintained, except for a short time after the HPIS stop (temporarily decrease below 10°C). The 3 primary pumps remain thus in operation during the whole transient. The total liquid discharge from the affected SG3 is about 17t for both scenarios DBA1 and DBA2. The total steam discharge from SG3 is about 5t for both scenarios. However, Steam mass releases from the intact SG1 are not stabilized at the end of the calculations due to the continuous opening of its RV. At the end of calculation, it is estimated to be 55t for both scenarios. For the calculation of the radiological releases from the intact SG1, only steam releases are considered. From a radiological point of view, the general trends of activity releases are the same for both scenarios, namely:
 - A minimal contribution to the activity releases from the intact steam generator despite the large amount of gas released from it;
 - A major contribution to the total activity released from the affected steam generator from the gaseous releases (in particular from Xe-133);
 - Except for noble gases and Cs-138 (derived from Xe-138) the major contribution of isotopes to the total activity is released by liquid discharge.

The total activity released by the affected steam generator, for all pathways combined (liquid and steam), is about 269 TBq in DBA2 scenario and about 47 TBq in DBA1 scenario. The difference is mainly in the activity released from the affected steam generator by noble gases, which is about 6 times lower in DBA1 scenario. For liquid releases, the main difference is related to the partitioning of Cs-138, the major contributor to Caesium activity. For DBA1 scenario Caesium is the main contributor to the released activity. However, for DBA2 scenario Iodine is by far the largest contributor to the total radiological releases.

PWR-1000 DBA case. Calculations were provided by TRACTEBEL, Bel V and CIEMAT.

- TRACTEBEL studied 1 scenario for DBA case: At transient initiation, $t = 10.0s$, a double-ended break of one U-tube at the top of the U-bundle of SG 1 is postulated to occur. For molecular iodine, the primary initial specific activity is about 1 GBq ^{131}I per ton of primary water. The initial total primary-to-secondary break flow rate is about 18.7 kg/s. Due to the loss of primary coolant, the level and the pressure in the pressurizer decrease, several control systems intervene in order to maintain the pressurizer pressure (increase of PRZ heaters electrical power) and level (increase of the CVCS charge flow rate) at this stage. Despite the automatic actions aiming at maintaining the pressurizer level and pressure, both continue to decrease. This eventually leads to the isolation of the pressurizer heaters and CVCS letdown. 1800s after the initiating event, it is assumed that Safety Injection Signal (signal S) is manually triggered (consistently with operating procedure) This leads to Reactor trip, turbine trip, AFW Start, MFW Isolation, MSIV Closure, Start of SI and Charging flow isolation. The SCRAM combined to the isolation of MFW leads to a collapse of the SGs water level. The MSIVs are closed at Safety Injection Signal, leading to an increase of the SGs pressure. Consequently, the affected SG 1 RV opens and stays stuck open because of the single failure, starting the releases to the atmosphere. Because of the stuck-open SG 1 RV, the affected SG 1 pressure decreases, in turn leading to an increase of the break flow. The AFW flow rate and the break flow are not able to compensate the SG RV mass flow, leading to SG 1 mass inventory decrease, until an equilibrium is reached around 2800s. Finally, 1320s after SCRAM, the operators isolate affected SG 1. More precisely, they stop AFW flow and close the RV of the affected SG 1. The transient simulation is ended when the break flow is ended.

Prior to reactor trip, the specific activities of the various systems remain roughly constant, except the affected SG that rises due to the break flow. The reactor trip, 1800s after initiator is immediately assumed to be followed by an iodine spiking. Due to the large release of activity from the fuel, the primary specific activity increases steadily. The specific activity of the affected SG 1 keeps increasing. This increase of specific activity of the affected SG 1 as a function of time in turn leads to a steady acceleration of flashing and partitioning release rates during the transient. Following the drop of the affected SG 1 level due to the reactor trip, the Net Liquid Height (NLH) above the break quickly drops below the minimum value, leading to a strong increase of the contribution of atomisation to releases. Finally, 1320s after SCRAM, the operators isolate affected SG 1, which stops the releases to the environment. At this stage, the total radiological releases from affected SG 1 is about 21.8 GBq ^{131}I . From this point (the end of the simulations) the plant still needs to be brought to RHRS conditions.

- CIEMAT studied one scenario for DBA case: The scenario analyzed is a double-ended guillotine break of a single steam generator tube near the top of the tube bundle at the pressurizer branch. The analysis assumes that the PORV of the ruptured SG remains fully open after its first actuation and stays so for 30 minutes. The initial break flow through the ruptured SG tube is approximately 39 kg/s. The flow decreases in response to the RCS depressurization. At 1800s after IE, approximately 70 t of primary coolant has been transferred from the RCS to the secondary side of the ruptured SG. The Flow through the stuck open PORV in the affected SG follows the same trend as the pressure. No core uncover occurs during the transient and as a consequence, core damage is not expected. In order to model the fission products (noble gases and iodine) entry into the RCS, injection rates of noble gases (Xe), and Iodine (I_2), have been calculated and included in a control function in the form of a table. The release rate (in kg/s of radionuclide) corresponds to the iodine spiking model. The iodine spiking is assumed to occur right at the reactor trip and only for the molecular iodine. The release rate may be assumed to increase by a factor of 500 and the removal rate drops to zero. The activity then rises linearly from equilibrium activity to higher and higher values for the duration of the event (usually eight hours). Note that this assumption does not lead to a "spike"; instead, it assumes a continuous and monotonous iodine accumulation until the event is terminated. In other words, this might be seen as a bounding case of iodine spike. The total amount of iodine injected in the RCS until 1800 s has been calculated to be 1.69e-05 kg. Given the iodine source, two approaches have been intended. "Class 4" results show that no iodine reaches the environment. However, this is just the expected outcome of a treatment in which no water-gas iodine partition is assumed to happen once in the secondary side. On the contrary, "new class" results estimates that an

18% of the iodine injected in the RCS ended up in the environment, which is practically 100% of the total mass flowing into the failed SG. Reality should be in between these two cases. Xe dynamics is qualitatively similar to that of iodine in the “new class” approach, as expected. The different growth and depletion kinetics with respect to iodine is associated with the different concentrations of both elements in the RCS. The integral activity release to the environment from the affected SG-C due to Xe-135 is $8.66e+06$ Bq, and due to I-131 is $2.39e+09$ Bq. It is assumed that after the 30 minutes of the event initiation the operators can identify the ruptured SG and, after its isolation, follow the prescribed SGTR EOPs procedures.

- Bel V studied 1 scenario for DBA case: In the current SGTR design basis case, the break uncover scenario is considered. The single failure assumption is applied on the relief valve of the secondary loop-3 where the break occurs. The later remains stuck open after its full opening. In this context, biased initial and boundary conditions are considered in order to increase the discharge flow rate and the time duration of the break uncover. In this way, the radiological release is maximised. No credit for operator actions is taken into account before 30 minutes from the start of the break. During this period, the SG tube break stays uncovered during the entire scenario. The release to the environment is carried out through the flashing, atomisation and partitioning mechanisms. It is assumed, that the so-called pre-spiking have already occurred before the simulation start, and that the RCS specific activity in the beginning of the accident is at the maximal level authorized by the technical specifications for transients. In addition to that, the spiking phenomenon occurs at $T=1800$ sec (i.e. at SCRAM), followed by the gradual release of the activity into the RCS. The activity release rate, used in this simulation, is taken from the utility experience. According to the scenario, the transient starts at the occurrence of a double-ended break located in the apex of the longest U-tube of loop-3 ($T=0$). Generally, at this elevation, the U-tubes are subjected to the strongest mechanical stresses. Before the rupture, the reactor was operating at full power under nominal operating conditions. As a consequence of the break, the primary coolant inventory, the pressure and the level of the pressurizer decrease. The control systems intervene in order to maintain both the pressurizer pressure and level. However, due to the continuous primary inventory loss, the charge flow could not compensate the break flow, the pressurizer pressure and level continue their decrease. Despite the non-compensation of the break flow by the charging, the scram setpoint by low primary pressure is not reached, and a manual SCRAM must be activated by the operator action, which is supposed after 30 min from the beginning of the transient. At $T=1801$ s, the letdown and the pressurizer heaters are isolated due to low pressurizer level. The main coolant pumps are supposed to be running during the entire transient period. After the reactor trip, the charging and the main feedwater are isolated. This is followed by the closure of the MSIV, the turbine trip, and the start of the auxiliary feedwater (AFW). The steam dump is also considered as not available. This causes a rise of the secondary pressure and consequently the relief pressure valves of all SGs open. Due to single failure assumption, the relief valve in the affected SG remains stuck fully open. The amount of steam released through the relief valve causes the primary to cool down. On the primary side, at $T=1895$ s, the continuous pressure decrease activates the high-pressure safety injection system (HPSI). This leads to a stabilization of the primary pressure around the maximum head of the HPSI in order to compensate the break flow and the shrinking due to cooldown. According to the emergency operating procedures EOPs, the operator isolates AFW towards the affected SG and isolates the affected SG by closing the faulted relief valve ($T=3122$ s). This ends radiological releases from the affected SG. From the beginning of the accident, the radioactive water of the primary circuit is transferred to the secondary side of the affected SG. Since the RCS is being constantly diluted, before the SCRAM, the radioactive water leakage leads to reduction of the RCS activity. At the same time, the activity transferred to the secondary side of the steam generator is considered to be accumulating inside the SG. Conservatively, the dilution of the SG secondary coolant with AFW is not considered, as with the activity release into the secondary circuit. At $T=1800$ s, the manual SCRAM starts the spiking phenomenon (pre-spiking phenomenon already considered before transient), leading to significant increase of the RCS activity. This results in a faster increase of the activity in the secondary side of the SG. The radioactive release by atomisation appears to be the dominant mechanism, followed by the partitioning and then flashing. All these releases are stopped at $T=3122$, when the

operator isolates the affected SG. The total released I131 activity to the environment is approximately 190 GBq.

PWR-1000 DEC A case. Calculations were provided by TRACTEBEL, Bel V and CIEMAT.

- TRACTEBEL studied one scenario for DEC A case: The simulated scenario is a Steam Generator Tube Rupture (SGTR) double-ended break on 3 tubes with Steam Line Break Outside Containment (SLBOUT) before Main Steam Isolation Valve (MSIV). The tubes break is located in the SG-1 (SG on the same loop as the pressuriser), at the bottom of the U-tubes bundle on the cold leg side (exit of the SG). The break is assumed to be happening on the shortest tubes. The reactor is assumed to be at HFP before the transient and a spiking phenomenon is occurring at SCRAM. The location of the SGTR break (bottom of the U-tubes) aims at maximizing the overfilling phenomenon for the affected SG.

At transient initiation, 2 events are postulated: a non-isolable SLBOUT before MSIV and a double-ended break of 3 U-tubes at the bottom (cold leg side) of the bundle of SG 1. The initiator leads to a rapid steam pressure decrease. Safety Injection Signal (Signal S) is triggered. This results in the reactor trip ($t = 0.75$ s), the isolation of the MSIV, the start of all SI pumps, the isolation of the MFW and the start of the AFW ($t = \text{SCRAM} + 110$ s = 110.7 s). The reactor cooling pumps are assumed lost at reactor trip due to the LOOP. The depressurization of the affected SG takes about 1200 s. The total (both hot leg and cold leg sides) primary-to-secondary break flow rate initially increases from about 60 kg/s to around 80 kg/s between $t = 0$ and $t = 500$ s. The HPSI flow rate compensates the loss of primary coolant through the SG's broken U-tubes resulting in a stabilization of the primary pressure around 110 bar abs. The primary-to-secondary break flow stabilizes around 80 kg/s. On the secondary side, the reactor trip leads to the level collapse in all SGs. After the isolation of the MFW and the closure of the MSIVs, the pressure increases in the intact SGs but stays under the pressure setpoint of the relief valves. The affected SG dries out due to the steam line double-ended break. At $t = 1210.7$ s the operators isolate the affected SG which includes the stop of AFW towards the affected SG 1. From this point on, the break flow rate becomes the only source of mass to the affected SG 1 adding about 80 kg/s of contaminated primary coolant. This results in a slightly slower increase of the mass inventory of the affected SG 1. At $t = 2600$ s, the affected SG starts overfilling: liquid water starts being spilled through the secondary break toward the environment. At $t = 3962.7$ s, the operators are allowed to connect the RHRS. The connection of the RHRS is not simulated. The calculation ends 10 minutes after the connection time of RHRS. During the transient, the RWST level decreases by only 12.5 %. In the core, the water level stays stable showing no degradation of the fuel for this scenario.

The primary-to-secondary break opening is immediately assumed to be followed by an iodine spiking. Due to the large release of molecular iodine (FP class 4) from the fuel, the inventory of class 4 in the RCS/vessel increases.

During the transient, the affected SG 1 is the responsible of the radiological releases to the environment. Before liquid discharge through the SLB, the partitioning phenomenon is the main contributor to the radiological releases to the environment for molecular iodine. When the SG 1 is full of liquid water, releases of molecular iodine with liquid water are happening provoking a much more increase of releases to the environment. At the end of the transient, considering an initial specific activity of 1 GBq/ton of primary water, the radiological releases to the environment are mainly constituted by $1.063e+11$ Bq released for the noble gases and $1.408e+11$ Bq released for the molecular iodine (4% are due to partitioning and releases with the steam phase before beginning of liquid water releases and the rest are due to the liquid discharges 96%).

- Bel V studied one scenario for DEC A case: The scenario considers a concurrent multiple SGTR (3 tubes) plus a non-isolable steam line break outside containment. The rupture is assumed to take place in the bottom of the cold side of the U-tube. In this case, less conservative initial and boundary conditions and operator grace time of 30 minutes are considered. In general, Best Estimate operating conditions are used. In the DEC-A scenario, the SG tube break is covered by water, but there is no SG overfilling. Therefore, neither atomisation, nor liquid discharge would be considered in the total radioactivity release.

Flashing and partitioning are considered the governing mechanisms for radioactivity release. According to the scenario, the transient starts at the occurrence of a non-isolable steam line break in the secondary loop-3 plus 3 tube double-ended break at the bottom position of the shortest U-tube. It is assumed, that the so-called pre-spiking have already occurred before the simulation start, and that the RCS specific activity in the beginning of the accident is at the maximal level authorized by the technical specifications for transients. In addition to that, the spiking phenomenon occurs at $T=0s$, followed by the gradual release of the activity into the RCS. The activity release rate, used in this simulation, is taken from the utility experience. After the break, the SCRAM set point is reached rapidly, leading to a loss of offsite power (LOOP). After the reactor trip, the charging and the main feedwater are isolated. This is followed by the closure of the MSIV, the turbine trip, and the start of the auxiliary feedwater (AFW) with a certain delays due to the time required to start the diesel generators. Shortly after the SCRAM, and due to the rapid depressurization of the system, the high pressure safety injection system is activated. Starting from the same time, the operator actions using the prescribed emergency operating procedures (EOPs) were credited. Subsequently, the operators identifies the faulted SG and stops the AFW towards SG3. Then according to the EOP's, the operator starts the cooldown via the intact SGs at a cooldown rate of 56K/h. However, since the primary pressure remains high, the operator starts opening of the PORV for a certain period of time in order to recover the pressurizer level. This is followed by a sequential stopping of the HPSI pumps. After that, the conditions for connecting the residual heat removal system are reached (RHRS). The primary pressure will decrease to low levels and will end the release into the environment. This ends the transient simulation.

In the beginning of the accident, the water content of the secondary part of the SG is drastically reduced and released into environment through the break in the main steam line. However, since the SG water in the beginning of the accident is not contaminated, but even diluted with the auxiliary feedwater, this does not lead to a massive release of radioactivity, and the dominant radioactivity release mechanism at the SG tube level remains the flashing. This is also due to a higher enthalpy of the primary side in the initial phase of the accident. However, quite soon in the course of the accident, the partitioning becomes more important than flashing in releasing the radioactivity. Even though, the radioactivity release by partitioning decreases with flowrate through the main steam line break, it remains dominant mechanism of radioactivity release into environment. The total released I131 activity to the environment is about 400GBq.

- CIEMAT studied one scenario for DEC A case: The DEC-A scenario analyzed is a concurrent isolable MSLB with the double-ended rupture of three steam generator tubes at the cold leg side tube sheet. The MSLB occurs outside the containment downstream MSIV. It is assumed that, at the time of tube break, the reactor operated at full power. The analysis considers that the LOOP occurs concurrently with the reactor trip. The MSLB concurrent with the rupture of three tubes of the SG-C is postulated to occur at time $t=0.0$ s. This transient causes a rapid depressurization in the steam line and in the affected SG and, as a consequence, a rapid decrease in the pressurizer pressure and pressurizer level. The reactor trip occurs at 4.0s after the beginning of the transient and is followed by the activation of the safety injection system on low primary pressure at 5.5 s. Several minutes after the initiation of the high safety injection, the flow injected in the RCS becomes sufficient to compensate the coolant loses through the SG tubes rupture. With the beginning of the cooldown operations (by the opening of the PORV in the intact SG at approximately 1200 s) the primary pressure decreases to the point where the plant operator initiates the RCS depressurization to equalize the pressure in the affected SG. The initial break flow through the ruptured SG tubes is approximately 95 kg/s. The flow decreases in response to the RCS depressurization and after 500 s it has an oscillatory behaviour due to the intermittent work of the PORV in the affected SG. The operator opening of the pressurizer PORV, at approximately 1951 s, conducts the recovery of the PRZ level and reduction of the break flow. At 3000 s after initiation of the transient, the integrated mass transferred through the primary break (from the RCS to the secondary side of the ruptured SG) is approximately 76125 kg. Due to the initial pressure decrease in the affected SG, the secondary side water reaches saturation and a fraction of it turns into steam. After the MSIV closure, the pressure in the broken SG rises up to the PORV set point and, as a consequence, steam is discharged to the environment. From

that time on the PORV valve of the affected SG acts intermittently, as designed. After 1951 s, with the reduction of the break flow, the mass inventory in the affected SG tends to stabilize. During the transient, the core cooling is ensured (no core uncover). The iodine spiking is assumed to occur right at the reactor trip and only for the molecular iodine. The activities of the Xe-135 and I-131 released to the environment are approximated assuming that in the time calculated (3000 s) the isotopes relative contribution is the one derived from the fission yield. The total amount of activity released due to Xe-135 is $6.82e+06$ Bq, and due to I-131 is $1.166e+09$ Bq.

PWR-1300 DBA case. Calculations were provided by BOKU.

- BOKU studied one scenario for DBA case: A leakage from the primary to the secondary side of the reactor occurs in loop 4 with an equivalent break area of 60 mm^2 (2 times the tube area). A single failure is assumed (the HPIS/LPIS trains and the EFW are not available in the affected loops (L3/4)). Operator actions are the depressurization of the secondary side (100 K/h) via the relief valves (RV) in the intact loops and the deactivation of the HPIS after 2100s to limit the loss of coolant through the break. During the first seconds of the accident the break mass flow rate reaches its maximum value of 45 kg/s. Due to the SCRAM and the pressure reduction at the Primary System, the mass flow rate through the break decreases fast until 1000s, when the HPIS pumps are activated. At 2100s, the secondary side cooling via the SG relief valves is initiated. The Primary System and Secondary System pressure are affected by the break and the following power reduction. The Primary System pressure is decreasing linearly in the first 240s after the break due to the gradual power reduction system. At about 1000s, the pressure starts increasing again due to activation of the HPIS. The pressure in the intact loops is decreasing after 2100s due to depressurization of the secondary side via the relief valves. The PRZ level decreases due to the SCRAM and depressurization of the primary system. However, the PRZ level begins to rise again, after the HPIS have been activated. After about 3000s the PRZ level starts to steadily decline again. The level in all intact SGs decreases after 2100s, when the secondary depressurization system is activated by the operator. This affects loop 3 differently than loop 1 and 2 because a repair case is assumed and no diesel generator is available for loop 3. The level in the affected SG (loop 4) slowly and steadily decreases after 2100s. All 4 RVs are opened automatically at the beginning of the transient and closed again before 2100s. The operator opened again the RV valves of the intact loops at 2100s. This action is primarily intended to depressurize the secondary side, which eventually results in a decrease of the primary side pressure. The RV in the affected loop is not opened by the operator to prevent emitting Fission Products to the environment. Fission products can only reach the environment through the relief valve. The released activity to the environment is not evaluated because of the limitation of RELAP5-3D: the transport of fission products can only be conducted in the liquid phase. BOKU will search for a solution of this problem.

PWR-1300 DEC A case. Calculations were provided by BOKU.

- BOKU studied one scenario for DEC A case: The initiating event of this transient simulation is a double-ended break of one SG tube in loop 4 with an equivalent break area of 600 mm^2 (2 times the tube area). This constitutes a primary to secondary system leak (PRISE). It is assumed that the relief valve in the affected loop is stuck in an open position after the first opening. All HPIS trains and all hydro accumulators (ACCs) are available at this scenario. However, the LPIS and the emergency feed water in the affected SG (due to isolation) are not available. Operator actions are the depressurization of the secondary side (100 K/h) via the relief valves (RV) in the intact SGs and the deactivation of the HPIS after 1800s to limit the loss of coolant through the break. During the first seconds of the accident the break mass flow rate reaches its maximum value of 46 kg/s and drops down rapidly as the pressure in the Primary System falls. Due to the SGTR, at 300 s the primary system pressure declines but stabilises due to the injection of the available HPIS system at around 700 s. On the secondary side the pressure in the intact SGs (loops 1 – 3) rises quickly before the closure of the MSIV due to the affected SG pressure increase, but finally declines as well after the SCRAM is initiated at 589 s on low Primary System Pressure (setpoint 132.5 bar abs). The Secondary System pressure rise

before the SCRAM initiation initiates the opening of the relief valve of SG 4 (loop 4). It is assumed that the relief valve of the affected SG is stuck open and does not close again throughout the simulation. This assumption penalizes the emission of Fission Products into the environment. The PRZ level decreases due to the break and finally rises and stabilises due to HPIS operation. Fission products can reach the environment through the relief valve in the affected loop. The released activity to the environment is not evaluated because of the limitation of RELAP5-3D: the transport of fission products can only be conducted in the liquid phase. BOKU will search for a solution of this problem.

2.6 Overview and discussion

2.6.1 Overview and discussion of LOCA calculation results

VVER calculations.

In total 5 partners analysed VVER type reactors (440 and 1000). The main accident scenario for the analysis was the same for all partners (double-ended break). However, due to some technology differences, applied modelling approach, different simulation tools and provided individual assumptions for the initial and boundary conditions the results of individual results were slightly different from each other. For the DBA case calculations and the double-ended break, the peak cladding temperatures (PCT) is varying from ~ 860 °C to ~ 1100 °C while for DEC-A case calculations varies from ~ 720 °C to ~ 900 °C. Differences in the peak cladding temperature calculations could be explained by differences in the boundary conditions, e.g., in HPIS and LPIS flowrate characteristics. Another reason is that in calculations some partners used the realistic initial conditions, however some others used conservative initial conditions, for example initial reactor power of 104% was assumed. Mentioned differences caused differences in the PCT temperatures calculated by partners and this difference was also reflected in other analysed parameters (i.e. thermo-mechanical analysis, number of failed rods, etc.).

Another calculation result summarized in this report is the activity released to the environment. This is the most important result to evaluate radiological consequences.

Partners who provided thermo-mechanical analysis found, that there is no damage of fuel cladding in the case of analysed LOCA for DBA and even in some case of DEC-A analysis. However, despite that most of the partners decided (for the DBA and DEC-A case analysis of fission product behaviour) to assume release from the fuel to the containment (or directly to environment for some partners) of the entire contents of the gas gap at the beginning of the transient. In this way, taken this very conservative approach, which will be revised in the Task 2.5, activity released to the environment through the design leakages were calculated. For VVER-440 reactor type, the calculated integral activity released to the environment is in the range from $\sim 9.5e+13$ Bq at beginning of release to $6.1e+15$ Bq during the first 80 000 s for a double-ended break in DBA conditions while for VVER-1000 reactor type, for the same conditions the calculated integral activity released to the environment is in the range from $\sim 3.5e+11$ Bq to $1.6e+13$ Bq during the first 60 000 s after the start of accident. The calculation results show that the results differ by 2 orders of magnitude. These differences could be caused by many reasons:

- initial conditions, already described for the PCT calculation difference;
- difference in initial inventory of fuel (difference in core power, in considered cycle, gap and fuel content);
- some of the partners calculated activity of only few important isotopes, others give total activity values;
- in some cases, different timing of the FP release into the containment determined by participants.

The total activity released into the environment consists of the activity released into the environment carried by aerosols, together with liquid and gas releases depending on the assumptions made by partners (filtered or non-filtered releases, operation of venting system or not, etc.). Activity release into the environment from liquid is always small. The activity release with aerosols depends on many factors (pressure, temperature, steam content in the containment, mass and energy of water, steam release from the primary circuit into the containment and other factors). As these aerosols condense onto containment surface and/or settle down to the containment sump, the containment activity in the gas phase decreases and thus the activity release into the environment is very low. The main and a more important contribution on the total activity release is the gaseous release through design leakage, which depends on the containment pressure. This activity release does not stop throughout the entire transient under consideration but continuously decrease as the pressure in the containment is decreasing. Thus, it is

important to consider a rather long time of calculation when the activity increase in the environment is relatively low comparing to initial phase. The time of the end of calculation, dependent on the selected scenarios and considered assumptions, was decided by each partner individually.

PWR calculations.

PWR type reactors were analysed by 4 partners but only 3 have provided FP activity releases. Similar situation was observed as in the case with VVER type reactors - accident scenarios for the analysis were similar for all partners, but due to some technology differences, provided individual assumptions for the initial and boundary conditions, and models/simulation tools, the obtained results were slightly different from each other.

For the DBA case calculations, the PCT is varying from ~ 750 °C to ~ 1050 °C. For DEC-A case calculations from ~ 1000 °C to even ~ 2250 °C. The highest temperature was reached by ENEA analysing PWR-900. This temperature was only for one analysed fuel group and for a short period of time. This did not cause fuel failures which could be out of the range of DEC-A conditions. Other groups did not reach 1250 °C.

For the PWR reactor type analysis, all partners provided thermo-mechanical analysis to realistically investigate possible cladding failures. For DBA cases, failure of the fuel rods varying from 1.4% to 33.1% of all fuel rods located in active core. For sure this difference depends on the simulated PWR type/model and for the assumptions and methods used for the simulation.

Result of the thermo-mechanical analysis have direct impact on the analysis of the fission product releases to the environment which is the most important result to evaluate radiological consequences. For the DBA case, the lowest results were $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{12}$ Bq (during the first 80000 s after the start of accident) and the highest 5.84×10^{14} Bq (during the first 86400 s after the start of accident). However, the highest value was achieved considering very conservative assumption that the released FP from fuel is directly transferred containment (without any retention in the primary circuit) and are homogeneously distributed within the containment. The release from containment to environment was considered taking the maximal flow rate according to containment design leakages and pressure. This is a very conservative approach, which will be revised by partner in Task 2.5.

In the case of DEC-A conditions, the lowest result was $\sim 8.7 \times 10^{13}$ Bq (during the first 172800 s after the start of accident) and the highest 5.84×10^{14} Bq (during the first 86400 s after the start of accident). However, as with the DBA case, the highest values are achieved by very conservative assumptions, which will be revised in Task 2.5.

As it was described for VVER type reactor analysis case, the differences in the calculations could be caused by many reasons, as: initial conditions and assumptions made (i.e. conservative assumption for the FP transport), difference in initial inventory of fuel, considered isotopes, timing of the FP release calculation end and mostly conservative assumption regarding the FP transport.

BWR calculations.

BWR reactor type calculations were provided only by one project partner, and it was provided only for DEC-A conditions. Calculated PCT is ~ 830 °C it is in between the values calculated for PWR and VVER. Thermo-mechanical analysis indicated total $\sim 55\%$ of all active zone was failed in the chosen DEC-A scenario. This also caused a high ($\sim 5.3 \times 10^{14}$ Bq) integral activity released into the environment during the first 2×10^5 s after the start of accident.

2.6.2 Overview and discussion of SGTR calculation results

VVER calculations.

In total 5 partners analysed VVER type reactors. The simulated accident is SGTR in DBA and DEC-A conditions. However, the initiator was not the same for all partners (break in the SG collector, break of SG tube(s), number/diameter of broken tubes,). Due to some technology differences and provided individual assumptions for the initial and boundary conditions (additional single/multiple failure(s), best estimate/penalized parameters), individual results were slightly different from each other. For the DBA case, the mass of the coolant discharged through the break from the primary circuit to the secondary circuit for the different scenarios varies from 40 t to 900 t. The affected SG total discharge (liquid and vapor) to the environment for the different provided scenarios varies

from 40 t to 850 t. Differences observed in the primary to secondary and secondary to environment discharges could be explained mainly by the differences in the SGTR break sizes, the IS duration, automatic procedures and operator actions and in the secondary to environment discharge capacities (SG relief and safety valves discharge capacities, setpoints, failures, operator actions, etc.). Also, differences occur due to boundary conditions, for example:

- Pressure in the primary side which is impacted by considering (or not) some assumptions (reactor scram signals, decay heat, reactor coolant pumps trip, cooling of the primary by the intact SG Relief valves, HPIS and LPIS failure/flowrate characteristics)
- Pressure in the affected SG which is also impacted by considering (or not) some assumptions (failure of the affected SG Relief valve and/or Safety valves, closure of the main steam isolation valves, isolation of the main/auxiliary feedwater)
- Realistic/Conservative initial conditions, for example initial reactor power of 104% was assumed by some partners.

Another calculation result summarized in this report is the activity released to the environment. This is the most important result to evaluate radiological consequences. For VVER-440 reactor type, the calculated integral activity released to the environment is in the range from $\sim 2.0 \times 10^{13}$ Bq to 4.6×10^{14} Bq. For VVER-1000 reactor type, the calculated integral activity released to the environment is in the range from $\sim 4 \times 10^{13}$ Bq to 2.23×10^{15} Bq. The calculation results show that the results may differ up to 2 orders of magnitude. These differences could be caused by many reasons:

- initial conditions, already described for the primary to secondary and secondary to environment discharges differences;
- difference in initial inventory of fuel)
- some of the partners calculated activity of only most important isotopes, others give total activity values;
- different timing of the FP release into the containment determined by participants.
- differences in the modelling (or not) of the spiking, pre-spiking, atomisation, flashing and partitioning phenomena.
- differences in considering (or not) the deposition and dilution of isotopes in the affected SG.

PWR calculations.

PWR type reactors were analysed by 5 partners. The simulated accident is SGTR in DBA and DEC-A conditions. However, the initiator was not the same for all partners (break position top/bottom, number/diameter of broken tubes). A similar situation was observed as in the case with VVER type reactors: Due to some technology differences and provided individual assumptions for the initial and boundary conditions (additional single/multiple failure(s), best estimate/penalized parameters), the individual results were slightly different from each other.

For PWR reactor type, the calculated integral activity released to the environment is in the range from $\sim 1.66 \times 10^9$ Bq to 2.69×10^{14} Bq. The lowest value was reached by CIEMAT PWR-1000 DEC-A analysis in which the secondary to the environment discharge is limited by considering an isolable SLBOUT.

The observed differences could be caused by many reasons:

- Pressure in the primary side which is impacted by taking into account (or not) some assumptions (reactor scram signals, decay heat, reactor coolant pumps trip, cooling of the primary by the intact SG Relief valves, HPIS and LPIS failure/flowrate characteristics ...);
- Pressure in the affected SG which is also impacted by taking into account (or not) some assumptions (additional isolable/non isolable SLB, failure of the affected SG Relief valve to close, failure of intact SG RV to open, closure of the main steam isolation valves, isolation of the main/auxiliary feedwater, ...);
- Realistic/Conservative initial conditions, for example initial reactor power of 102% was assumed by some partners;
- difference in initial inventory of fuel;
- some of the partners calculated activity of only most important isotopes, others give total activity values;
- different timing of the FP release into the containment determined by participants;
- differences in the modelling (or not) of the spiking, pre-spiking, atomisation, flashing and partitioning phenomena;

- differences in taking into account (or not) the deposition and dilution of isotopes in the affected SG.

3 Conclusions & foreseen improvements

In 2.3 task partners covered large amount of the LWR and wide range of the LOCA and SGTR accidents at DBA and DEC-A conditions. In total 36 individual reports covering the major LOCA and SGTR accident scenarios in the PWR, EPR, VVER and BWR reactors were submitted to the share point of the project. These reports were elaborated according to a predefined template (see Annex 1 & 2) allowing to define the expected information on the calculations (i.e. reactor models, calculation hypotheses/assumptions, etc) and the expected results from thermal-hydraulic, thermo-mechanical and FP transport and behaviour analysis. These latter will also help to gather the calculation results for the foreseen database to be built during the project.

In Task 2.3 first runs of reactor calculations were performed. Partners were used existing calculation schemes composed of different modelling tools of various levels of details providing a large range of results. Reflecting on the given tasks the partners used mostly modelling tools currently used for the reactor accident calculations without going into detailed modelling of all the processes occurring from the reactor core to the environmental releases during the transients. For the non-modelled processes in some cases decoupling factors and arbitrary assumptions usually conservative assumptions were used. The results of these calculations allowed to highlight where improvements in the simulation tools and calculation schemes could be made to better estimate the environmental releases during LOCA and SGTR transients under DBA and DEC-A conditions. Some of these improvements will be made during the project and are already in progress in the WP3 and WP4.

Without going into details, different types of improvements are planned within the project which can be divided into three main categories:

- Improvements of the calculation chains and methodologies (i.e. by coupling of more mechanistic simulation tools, statistical approaches for fuel rod clad ruptures)
- Improvements of plant models (i. e. by updating approach of core modelling, upgrading nodalization schemes),
- Developments/improvements of mechanistic modelling for a detailed modelling of some important processes (i.e. fuel rod clad deformation and rupture, clad secondary hydriding, HBS, FP transport and chemistry)
- Improvement of computational models (i. e. by developing of new cladding models better corresponding to the experimental data and better evaluating possible cladding failures, including user-driven correlations like iodine spiking modelling)

Annex A Guidance on the different annexes.

To collect the necessary information resulting from the models/calculation by the different partners a template has been created in close collaboration with the different partners. Two similar templates have been created: one for LOCA calculations and one for SGTR calculations.

For every performed calculation a filled in template is required (e.g. TRACTEBEL has 2 documents, 1 for the SGTR DBA calculation and one for the SGTR DEC-A calculation).

The two templates are presented in Annex A1 and Annex A2.

Annex A1: Template for LOCA

R2CA-Task 2.3: Template for LOCA

General information: partners are expected to deliver one complete document for every scenario. e.g. if a partner will perform 4 separate calculations (LOCA DBA; LOCA DEC-A; SGTR DBA; SGTR DEC-A), 4 separate documents are expected.

Company name:

Authors:

1. SHORT DESCRIPTION OF ANALYSED PLANT AND CODE MODELLING

1.1. This paragraph should contain the plant description. The focus should be limited to the main components of the reactor (useful to identify the differences between the studied reactors in the framework of the analysed case) and not on the general design of the reactor (e.g. for LOCA it is important where the safety injection is connected to the primary circuit).

List of the relevant parameters of the plan such as: thermal power, main characteristics of the core, thermal hydraulic parameters of the primary and secondary cooling circuit, provided safety systems which will be used in the analysis.

1.2. Scenario description

This paragraph should contain a general description of the scenario, including:

- Initiator events (e.g. break size and location - see description of scenario's presented in the scenario document (Task 2.2), etc.);
- Boundary and initial conditions:
 - o Operational point before the start of the transient;
 - o Initial core inventory *and FP distribution (if available and possible to share this information)*; burn-up; initial state of the fuel/clad and recall of main assumptions (i.e. average of different fuel assemblies)
 - o etc...
- Information of the safety systems involved (including their trigger point).
- Information on the operator actions (including their trigger point).
- Design leakage to environment ((%vol/day)

1.3. Modelling

This paragraph should detail the modelling tools and, selected for this analysis, reactor model.

- Description of the calculation method (calculation schemes, decoupling factors, main assumptions and hypotheses (including primary coolant activity or FP inventory...etc.;
- Description of modelling tools, versions, reference, other important useful information (you can refer to task 2.1.2 if it seems useful);
- Description of the developed plant model for the modelling tool (MELCOR, ASTEC,),
- Main assumptions and hypothesis, nodalization scheme,
- Other related information (including potential limitations in the calculation methods).

2. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

2.1. Steady-state calculation results

This paragraph should give the results of the steady-state, before the start of the transient, with the main parameters (presented in tabular form).

Minimum values that should be presented:

- Core thermal power (MWth) power and FP distribution;
- Pressure in primary loop (MPa);

- Primary loop mass flow rate (kg/s);
- Water inlet temperature in the core (K);
- Water outlet temperature in the core (K) (not for BWR);
- Main steam line temperature (K) (for BWR);
- Primary water inventory (kg).

Optional parameters that can be given:

- *Feedwater mass flow rate (kg/s);*
- *Feedwater temperature (K);*
- *Pressurizer level (%);*
- *Pressure in steam-generator (MPa);*
- *Main steam line temperature (K);*
- *Recirculation ratio in the SG (-);*
- *Secondary loop mass flow rate (kg/s);*
- *Other.*

Additionally, a comparison between calculation results and power plant data may be added by partners on a voluntary base.

2.2. LOCA-Transient

- *Main Events*
Table with the main events vs. time and eventually some remarks
- *Thermohydraulic:*
Minimum parameters that should be presented:
 - Mass flow rate through the break (water and steam) vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Primary loop pressure vs. time; (MPa)
 - Water level in the core vs. time; (m from the bottom of active core)
 - Mass flow rate of injected water from accumulators, ECCS and /or other safety systems vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Containment pressure vs. time; (MPa)
 - Containment spray flow rate vs time; (kg/s)
 - Leakages to environment (see also FP behaviour) (kg/s or Bq/s)
Optional parameters
 - Integrated break mass flow; (kg/s)
 - Temperature in the primary loop; (K)
 - Temperature in the containment (in liquid & gas phase); (K)
 - Reactor circulation pump speed vs. time evolution; (rpm)
- *Fuel thermo-mechanics & core degradation: -Some proposed parameters for the results discussion:*
Minimum values that should be presented:
 - Number of failed fuel rods;
 - Produced hydrogen mass; (kg)
 - Cladding failure time; (K)
 - Cladding failure elevation from the active fuel bottom; (m)
 - Peak cladding temperature in different groups of fuel assemblies; (K)

Optional parameters

- Location of failed fuel rods;
- Pressure in the fuel rods vs. time; (MPa)
- Cladding hoop strain (+ stress?) at failure time and elevation; (% , (MPa))
- Cladding oxidation; (μm)
- Others;

- *FP behaviour (FP given preferably as isotopes)*
 - Minimum parameters that should be presented:
 - Release of FP (eventually in time evolution) for each leakage path; (Bq)
 - Main FP* (I, Cs, Xe, Kr...) release rates in primary circuit vs time (kg/s)
 - Activity rate evolution vs time in the containment liquid & gas phase; (Bq/h)
 - Main FP retention in the primary circuit or main FP releases rate in the containment (Kg/s);
 - Optional:
 - Evolution vs time of FP mass or concentration in the containment liquid and gas phase and eventually on containment surfaces;(% in function of h)
 - Iodine speciation evolution (particulate, I₂, RI,...); (%)

(*) a list of main isotopes has to be established taking into account the most relevant isotopes for RC evaluation.

3. MAIN REMARKS

Any observations on performed calculations

Annex A2: Template for SGTR

R2CA-Task 2.3: Template for SGTR

General information: partners are expected to deliver one complete document for every scenario. e.g. if a partner will perform 4 separate calculations, 4 separate documents are expected.

Company name:

Authors:

1. SHORT DESCRIPTION OF ANALYSED PLANT AND CODE MODELLING

1.1. This paragraph should contain the plant description. The focus should be limited to the main components of the reactor (useful to identify the differences between the studied reactors) and not on the general design of the reactor.

List of the relevant parameters of the plan such as: thermal power, main characteristics of the core, thermal hydraulic parameters of the primary and secondary circuit, engineering safety systems.

1.2. Scenario description

This paragraph should contain a general description of the scenario, including:

- Initiator events (e.g. break size and location - see description of scenario's presented in the scenario document (Task 2.2), etc.);
- Boundary and initial conditions:
 - o Operational point before the start of the transient;
 - o Info about initial core inventory (*If available and possible to share this information*); burn-up; initial state of the fuel/clad and recall of main assumptions (i.e. average of different fuel assemblies)
 - o etc...
- Information of the safety systems involved.
- Information on the operator actions.

1.3. Modelling

This paragraph should detailed the modelling tools and, selected for this analysis, reactor model.

- Used codes, versions and reference;
- Description of the calculation method;
- Description of the specific code plant model (MELCOR, ASTEC,),
- Main assumptions and hypothesis, nodalization scheme.....

2. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

2.1. Steady-state calculation results

This paragraph should give the results of the steady-state, before the start of the transient, with the main parameters (presented in tabular form).

Minimum parameters that should be presented:

- Core thermal power; (MWth)
- Pressure in pressurizer; (Bar)
- Pressure in the steam generator; (Bar)
- Inlet temperature in the core; (K)
- Outlet temperature in the core; (K)
- Primary loop mass flow rate; (kg/s)
- Primary inventory; (kg)
- SG liquid mass inventory; (kg)

Optional parameters that can be given:

- SG Narrow range level;
- *Feedwater mass flow rate; (kg/s)*
- *Feedwater temperature; (K)*
- *Main steam line temperature. (K)*
- *Pressurizer level; (%)*
- *Recirculation ratio in the SG; (-)*
- *Allowed activity in the primary/secondary circuit; (Bq/m³)*

Additionally a comparison between calculation results and power plant data may be added by partners on a voluntary base.

2.2. SGTR-Transient

- *Main Events*
May be simply a table with the main events (safety signals, operator action, key events, etc...) vs. time and eventually some remarks.
- *Thermohydraulic:*
Minimum parameters that should be presented:
 - Primary pressure vs. time; (Bar)
 - Secondary pressure vs. time; (Bar)
 - Inlet core temperature; (K)
 - Outlet core temperature; (K)
 - Safety Injection mass flow rate vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Primary mass inventory vs. time; (kg)
 - Nuclear core power vs. time(Mw)
 - Primary mass flow rate vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Primary subcooling vs. time; (K)
 - Break mass flow rate (water and steam) vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Feedwater mass flow vs. time; (kg/s)
 - Feedwater temperature vs. time; (K)
 - SG mass inventory vs. time; (kg)
Optional parameters
 - Pressuriser heater power vs. time;
 - Core water level vs. time;
 - Integrated break mass flows;
- *Fuel thermo-mechanics & core degradation: -Some proposed parameters for the results discussion:*
Optional parameters
 - Cladding temperature at failure time and elevation; (K)
- *FP behaviour (FP given preferably as isotopes)*
Minimum values that should be presented:
 - Release of FP (eventually in time evolution) for each leakage path; (Bq)
 - Release of fission products in the primary circuit (spiking phenomena, integral + rate); (Bq, Bq/s)
 - Iodine speciation evolution (particulate, I₂, RI,...); (%)

Optional:

- Mass transfer from the primary to the secondary (liquid/steam phase); (kg/h)
- Specific activity in the SG, primary circuit vs. time; (Bq)

(*) a list of main isotopes has to be established taking into account the most relevant isotopes for RC evaluation.

3. MAIN REMARKS

Any observations on performed calculations